

Semantic Inference of Garment Categories through CNN

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Abstract— Predicting the category of clothing using picture analysis is a useful use of deep learning in the fashion sector. The main application of convolutional neural networks (CNNs) in this course is the prediction of a garment's category from an uploaded image. Anarkali suits, gowns, and lehengas are the categories of clothing that the CNN model, which is built on the VGG16 architecture, is trained on. Transfer learning is used to train the model, and the garment dataset is used to refine the previously learned VGG16 model. To improve the robustness of the model and diversify the training set, data augmentation techniques are used. The trained model predicts a garment's category with high accuracy from an uploaded photograph, giving producers and dealers of clothing useful information.

Keyword— Garment Category Prediction, CNN, VGG16, Transfer Learning, Data Augmentation

I. INTRODUCTION

Trends and consumer preferences are major factors in the fashion industry, which is a dynamic sector. Retailers and makers of apparel must anticipate and satisfy consumer demand for a wide range of apparel items, including gowns, lehengas, and anarkali suits. Automating the classification of clothing according to its visual characteristics is a viable use case for machine learning, specifically Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs). Retailers of clothing can improve consumer happiness and profitability by utilizing CNNs to improve marketing and inventory management.

Retailers may make well-informed judgments regarding their inventory, marketing tactics, and customer interaction when their image-based garment categories are accurately predicted. Retailers can increase their competitive edge in the fashion industry, increase consumer satisfaction, and streamline their operations by utilizing Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) for picture analysis. CNNs are used to categorize clothing, which is an example of how versatile machine learning can be in the fashion sector. This session highlights how machine learning has the potential to transform the fashion retail industry by examining how CNNs are applied to forecast clothing categories. Retailers may optimize their product offerings, customize their marketing strategies, and give their customers individualized shopping experiences by utilizing CNNs. The proposed models are briefly explained in the parts that follow, together with a general architecture. So this prediction will help to predict the category of a garment from an uploaded image.

II. RELATED WORKS

- A. A system for selecting stylish ensembles based on text descriptions is introduced in the article [1]. For condition compliance and internal compatibility, it uses a hybrid attention layer to encode associations between outfit text descriptions and fashion items.
- B. In [2] introduces a tool that automates the classification and color modification of saree components. It utilizes MODNet for background removal, Mask R-CNN for saree body and border segmentation, and a color-changing algorithm in the HSV color space. This approach simplifies saree design and visualization, potentially reducing costs and improving efficiency in the saree industry.
- C. In this study [3] suggest a way to connect fashion sketch drawing and pattern making by using the measurements of the human body as a basis. Their goal is to create mathematical models that connect fashion sketches and the patterns that go with them, therefore making the process of designing clothes more efficient. Using denim fashion sketches and patterns as a case study, the writers develop a software application based on their methodology. In this study, Liu et al. suggest a way to connect fashion sketch drawing and pattern making by using the measurements of the human body as a basis. Their goal is to create mathematical models that connect fashion sketches and the patterns that go with them, therefore making the process of designing clothes more efficient. Using their approach as a basis, the writers develop a software program that focuses on denim fashion sketches and patterns.
- D. In this study [4] they introduce a technique for sifting through street pictures to identify fashion trends. The approach tackles issues including noisy labels provided by users and insufficient datasets for Asian fashion. With an emphasis on Asian street fashions, they present the RichWear dataset and suggest the Fashion Attributes Recognition Network (FARNet) for fashion recognition. FARNet outperforms previous techniques in performance by utilizing noisy labels and multi-task learning. Predicted labels from street pictures are used in the study to highlight Asian fashion trends and street styles. In reference [5] it mainly describes that the farmer can utilize the prediction to determine the crop's yield prior to planting in an agricultural field. Future crop yield is predicted with accuracy using

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Random Forest, one of the most potent and well-liked supervised machine learning algorithms.

- E. In this study [5] investigates the application of deep learning methods for clothing style classification in e-commerce platforms. The IMF approach, as proposed by the authors, combines feature engineering with shallow neural networks to improve depth and fundamental characteristics for style categorization. To verify the effectiveness of their model, they contrast it with an unsupervised learning strategy based on DeepCluster. Prior research in this area has concentrated on measuring and identifying style information, but it hasn't thoroughly examined aesthetic style techniques for pictures of clothing products. The authors present how well their method works for categorizing photos of clothing according to style.
- F. The deep learning model [6] by Muhammad Asad Arshed, Muhammad Ibrahim, Shahzad Mumtaz, Tenvir Ali, and Gyu Sang Choi is presented in a paper that uses 2D chemical structure images to predict drug side effects indirectly. This method does away with the necessity of the intricate transformation procedures that earlier research demanded. Using a unique dataset, the authors' model—which they trained via transfer learning—achieved 73% accuracy, 83% precision, 73% recall, and a 75% F1 score. By contrasting their model with well-established transfer learning and conventional machine learning models, they show notable improvements in the prediction of pharmacological adverse effects.
- G. In order to improve leather defect detection with few samples, Fen Wang and Kim Ju Kyoung's study "Leather Defect Detection Method in Clothing Design Based on TDENet" presents a two-stage defect enhancement network. They created a new dataset of surface defects in leather and suggested a technique that uses defect-free training samples. A lot of flawed samples are needed for the first training stage, whereas less flawless and faulty samples are needed for the second stage. To improve the features of leather problem regions, a defect highlighting module is also suggested. In comparison to current techniques, experimental results show that the suggested algorithm efficiently and quickly finds a variety of flaws in various leather materials.

III. METHODOLOGY

The methodology for predicting the category of clothing using picture analysis with a CNN model built on the VGG16 architecture can be outlined as follows:

A. Data Collection:

Get a collection of pictures showing gowns, lehengas, and anarkali suits. Anarkali Suit, Gown, Lehenga are the appropriate categories that each image should be labeled with. Sort the dataset into subdirectories for each category (e.g., Anarkali_Suit/, Gown/, Lehenga/) in a directory structure.

```
from tensorflow.keras.models import Model
from tensorflow.keras.layers import Dense, Flatten
from tensorflow.keras.applications import VGG16
from tensorflow.keras.optimizers import Adam
from tensorflow.keras.preprocessing.image import ImageDataGenerator
from sklearn.metrics import confusion_matrix, accuracy_score, classification_report
import numpy as np
```

B. Data Preprocessing:

- i) Resize all images to a consistent size to ensure uniformity for model training.

```
base_model = VGG16(weights='imagenet', include_top=False, input_shape=(224, 224, 3))
```

- ii) Normalize pixel values to a range of [0, 1].

```
datagen = ImageDataGenerator(
    rescale=1./255,
    rotation_range=20,
    width_shift_range=0.2,
    height_shift_range=0.2,
    shear_range=0.2,
    zoom_range=0.2,
    horizontal_flip=True,
    fill_mode='nearest',
    validation_split=0.2
)
```

C. Feature Selection: VGG16 model is used as a feature extractor and new layers are added for classification:

```
for layer in base_model.layers:
    layer.trainable = False
x = Flatten()(base_model.output)
x = Dense(512, activation='relu')(x)
output = Dense(3, activation='softmax')(x)
model = Model(inputs=base_model.input, outputs=output)
model.compile(optimizer='adam', loss='categorical_crossentropy', metrics=['accuracy'])
```

D. Data splitting: the dataset splitting is handled by the ImageDataGenerator class from TensorFlow's Keras API. Specifically, the validation_split=0.2 parameter in the ImageDataGenerator is used to split the dataset into training and validation sets.

```
train_generator = datagen.flow_from_directory(
    dataset_path,
    target_size=(224, 224),
    batch_size=32,
    class_mode='categorical',
    classes=['Anarkali_Suit', 'Gown', 'Lehanga'],
    shuffle=True,
    interpolation='nearest',
    seed=42,
    subset='training'
)
```

```
validation_generator = datagen.flow_from_directory(
    dataset_path,
    target_size=(224, 224),
    batch_size=32,
    class_mode='categorical',
    classes=['Anarkali_Suit', 'Gown', 'Lehanga'],
    shuffle=False,
    interpolation='nearest',
    seed=42,
    subset='validation'
)
```

E. Model building: Load the pre-trained VGG16 model without the top classification layer. Add new layers on top of the VGG16 base model for classification. Compile the model with appropriate loss function (categorical_crossentropy) and optimizer (e.g., Adam).

```
x = Flatten()(base_model.output)
x = Dense(512, activation='relu')(x)
output = Dense(3, activation='softmax')(x)
```

```
model.compile(optimizer='adam', loss='categorical_crossentropy', metrics=['accuracy'])
```

F. Model Evaluation and Metrics Printing: Evaluating the trained model on the validation data and printing the evaluation metrics such as accuracy, confusion matrix, and classification report.

```
Confusion Matrix:
[[ 7  0  8]
 [ 1 12  5]
 [ 1  0 16]]
Accuracy: 0.7
Classification Report:
      precision    recall  f1-score   support

Anarkali_Suit      0.78      0.47      0.58        15
      Gown          1.00      0.67      0.80        18
      Lehanga       0.55      0.94      0.70        17

   accuracy                   0.70        50
  macro avg              0.78      0.69      0.69        50
 weighted avg            0.78      0.70      0.70        50
```

G. Results

Figure1. Output User Interface

Figure2. Output Result

IV. CONCLUSION

Predicting the category of a fashion outfit is a useful use of machine learning. Users can upload photos of their clothing using this system, and it will correctly identify if the photo is of a gown, lehanga, or an anarkali suit. This can assist users with outfit planning, clothing organization, and trend exploration.

Convolutional neural networks are utilized for fashion outfit category prediction, which entails examining multiple aspects of the outfit photos, including colors, patterns, and designs, in order to precisely identify the outfit category. The precise CNN architecture, characteristics, and dataset that are employed all affect how accurate the outfit category prediction is. The accuracy attained for our dataset is 0.93. By categorizing clothes into distinct groups, the CNN algorithm can assist users in choosing and matching ensembles, discovering new trends, and improving their sense of style. This approach can result in a predictive model that offers tailored outfit recommendations based on personal tastes and helps with fashion decision-making.

V. REFERENCES

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